

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See informed consent sheet

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized transcript of the recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	02/06/2021
Name of the interviewer	FRANCISCO VELASCO CABALLERO
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	BLAS JESÚS NIETO LÓPEZ
Affiliation of the expert	MUNICIPALITY OF NAVA DEL REY (VALLADOLID)
Position/Job description	WATCHDOG OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF NAVA DEL REY
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	
Area of expertise	WATCHDOG
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	In your opinion, what is the impact that increasing population movements from the countryside to cities have on local governments?
	Currently, the municipality is losing little population. The population that emigrates normally goes to <i>Medina del Campo</i> (which is the head of the county) and Valladolid. More than migration, the population reduction is mainly due to the mortality of the very old, which is numerous. On the contrary, there is currently a strong flow of immigration, for agricultural activities (vineyards), especially from Romania. This immigrant population is normally registered, so they are residents of the municipality.
1.1	<p><i>Do you know any public policies or best practices regarding the changing urban-rural relationships? Please consider practices in the following five areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Local responsibilities and public services.</i> - <i>Local financial arrangements.</i> - <i>Structure of local government.</i> - <i>Intergovernmental relations of local governments.</i> - <i>People's participation in local decision-making.</i>
	The City Council has approved an ordinance to promote the birth rate, which through (modest) financial aid, aims above all for the young people of the municipality to form families. In any case, they are small financial aid, not decisive. Apart from this, the Provincial Council has some more important aids (most of it for the promotion of employment) with more magnitude or value for the retention of the population in the municipality.

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2	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?
	Investment in infrastructure is preferable. In particular, the improvement of the CL-602 highway, which communicates with Medina del Campo, is very convenient. Improving communication with Medina, which is the largest municipality in the county, can encourage part of the population of Nava del Rey to continue working here, but live in Medina. But on the other hand, better communication with Medina is essential for the proper functioning (supplies, etc.) of the companies based in Nava del Rey.

LOCAL FINANCIAL ARRANGEMENTS

4	Do you know what approximate percentage of municipal income comes from municipal taxes, transfers (state, autonomous and provincial), and service fees?
	Approximately, own revenues (fees and taxes) are half of the municipal revenues.
5	How do you value this income structure?
	The structure is adequate. Usually, the municipality does not have an income deficit, but rather spending problems. The fees for services are well adjusted, they are not burdensome, nor are direct taxes high. Regarding the IBI or yearly property taxes, the tax rate could increase when it refers to rural rents since the owners of these country houses normally show more taxable capacity. The urban yearly property taxes could now be a bit high (tax rate of 0.75%), although it has already been reduced in recent years. In any case, the urban property tax is not high either, given that the cadastral values of the buildings (many of them old, built around 1890) are low.
6	Do you consider that the municipality has good financing?
	6.1. If the previous question is negative, where should the best financing come from: From municipal taxes, State /autonomous/

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	provincial transfers, services, or indebtedness?
	The part of the transfers could be increased, especially to make them more unconditional (the Autonomous ones and those of the Provincial Council), but it is good that there is a part of the income from own taxes.
7	<p><i>Do you consider that municipal financing influences the migratory flow towards large cities?</i></p> <p><i>7.1. How? In which way?</i></p> <p><i>7.2. could you offer an example?</i></p>
	A reduction or cut in taxes would not affect depopulation, it would not even serve in a qualified way to attract companies, since currently, municipal taxes are not high. Currently, there are good conditions for locating companies in the municipality (there is even industrial land available for companies). The greatest need for economic activity in the municipality is the improvement of land communications.
8	Does the aging of the population affect the budget of your municipality?
	It affects only moderately since specific services for the elderly are not managed by the City Council.
9	What other demographic changes affect the income structure?
	There is no particularly relevant factor.
10	In your opinion, does the municipality have a scattered population?
	No, the population is highly concentrated in the urban nucleus.
11	To what extent does dispersion affect municipal income and expenditures?
	This question has been already indirectly answered.
12	In order to promote the development of rural municipalities, are more effective the public grants or unconditional financial transfers?
	The public subsidies directed to concrete objectives (such as promoting employment) are very useful. Although in general, it is better that the subsidies are unconditional, it is positive that through the finalist conditions the municipal activity is directed to a certain extent.

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13	In order to attract towards or retain the population in the rural municipalities, which municipal income structure do you consider would be more favorable?
	Population retention depends very little on the municipal budget.

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

CURRENT TRANSFERS

14	How do you assess the amount of municipal income from current transfers?
	Generally, it is adequate.
15	From whom they receive these transfers? In what percentages?
	The City Council receives transfers from the State (participation in State tax revenues), the Autonomous Community of Castilla y León, and the Valladolid Provincial Council. The Autonomous Community grants subsidies to promote employment, tourism, and the hiring of people with disabilities. A good part of the grants is only for small municipalities.
15.1	Have they been constant during the last legislature?
	They are relatively stable transfers.
16	Does the City Council receive current transfers from the Provincial Government?
	The Provincial Government gives aid for the "We Grow Program" (for childcare centers) and for the promotion of employment. The provincial government subsidizes but does not manage the corresponding services (The City Council itself does it).
17	If the municipality is in a single province Autonomous Community: does it receive current transfers from the Community?
	It is not the case.
18	Do you consider the current transfers received by the City Council to be adequate?
	This question has already been answered in previous responses.

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

CAPITAL TRANSFERS

19	What is your opinion on the municipal income that comes from capital transfers?
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	Capital transfers (to carry our Works) are essential for the City Council.
20	What does the City Council dedicate capital transfers to?
	For the maintenance of public roads.

CONDITIONAL GRANTS

21	How do you assess the conditional transfers that your Council receives?
	In general, conditional grants are well designed, they do not finance activities not wanted by the City Council, although a greater margin of autonomy for the City Council would be desirable to specify the destination of the grant.
22	To what extent are conditional subsidies channeled through the Provincial Plan for Constructions and Services?
	Investments in works are channeled through the Provincial Works and Services Plan, which is biannual. For the elaboration of the Provincial Plan, the City Council previously sends a survey with its investment needs, a survey that is normally respected by the Provincial Council. All the works are co-financed by the City Council, although sometimes the municipal contribution is very small, almost all of which is paid by the Provincial Council. For example, provincial subsidies for energy efficiency are financed 95% by the Provincial Council (and even for the remaining 5%, which corresponds to the City Council, the Provincial Council offers long-term loans).

PROVINCIAL SERVICES

23	Does the Provincial Government provide any service in the municipality? Which one?
	The Provincial Government provides basic social services. The headquarters of the services is in Nava del Rey, although they serve other nearby small municipalities. The specialized social services are based in Medina del Campo.
24	Do you think that the City Council could manage these services if it had better financing?
	Not at the beginning. For these services, a certain scale is necessary, which makes it convenient for them to be provided by the Provincial Council or the Autonomous Community. Services such as garbage collection are provided through a community, which includes several municipalities around Medina del Campo, which shows that higher scale management than the municipal one is convenient. The Provincial Council helps the community financially. Another

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	<p>association in which the City Council participates, and which also works well, is the “association of water services”, which is based on a water treatment plant from the Duero River (the association provides the supply service “in discharge”, and the home distribution is done by the council itself).</p> <p>Concerning this, a Commonwealth of General Interest is currently in the process of being created that aims to cover more municipal services of the town halls in an area of 15 Km around Medina del Campo. The usefulness of this initiative is not clear. The sectoral association works well, and taking the reference of a geographical area of 15 Km, is in principle arbitrary. It is better to promote sectoral associations, such as waste.</p>
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TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

25	Does your City Council receive technical assistance from the Provincial Government? And from the Autonomous Community?
	Yes. Legal and accounting advice from the Provincial Council is important, and it works well. Sometimes there is a certain overlap of functions between the Provincial Council and the Territorial Delegations of the autonomous Community.
26	Does the Provincial Government collaborate in municipal procedures, such as tax or payroll management?
	The City Council has delegated the tax management (not only the collection but also the liquidation of the taxes) in the Provincial Council (REVAL), which works well.

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